

Article title: Immunity, Infections and Vitamins

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Immunity, Infections and Vitamins

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this review is to explore the available scientific literature and elucidate whether infections, including COVID-19, can cause hypovitaminoses, and on the other hand, may hypovitaminoses be the risk factor for the weaker immune response to infection. Methods include literature search (PubMed, ScienceOpen). Conclusion: optimal nutritional status, especially of vitamins A, C, E and D, is important for the normal functioning of the immune system. It seems that infections can increase the expenditure of vitamins A and C, and *vice versa*, lower levels of vitamin A and C may be associated with an increased susceptibility for infections and increased risk for the development of severe forms of infection, including COVID-19. Immunomodulatory vitamins D and E are important for the optimization of the immune response to various infections, protecting thus the host from both severe forms of infection and hyperinflammatory immune response with the development of cytokine storm and/or autoimmune processes, which is especially important in the context of COVID-19 pandemic. It seems that vitamin K deficiency is an important modifiable risk factor for the development of severe forms of COVID-19 and that vitamin D and vitamin K deficiency are interrelated, and represent potentially a synergistic effect on the severity of COVID-19.

KEYWORDS: vitamins; immune system; infections; COVID-19

INTRODUCTION

The discovery of the vitamins was a major scientific achievement in understanding of health and disease. In 1912, Casimir Funk originally coined the term *vitamine*. The puzzle of each vitamin was solved through the meticulous work and contributions of epidemiologists, physicians, physiologists, and chemists. Experimental physiology with animal models played a fundamental role in nutrition research and greatly shortened the period of human suffering from vitamin deficiencies. Ultimately it was the chemists who isolated the various vitamins, deduced their chemical structure, and developed methods for synthesis of vitamins¹. The role nutrition plays in supporting the immune system is well-established. Available mechanistic and clinical data show that vitamins, including A, B₆, B₁₂, C, D, E, and folate; trace elements, including zinc, iron, selenium, magnesium, and copper; and the omega-3 fatty acids eicosapentaenoic acid and docosahexaenoic acid play an important role in supporting the immune system².

VITAMIN A

Vitamin A is the term used to describe compounds with the qualitative biological activity of retinol. Vitamin A active retinoids occur in nature in three forms: alcohol-retinol, aldehyde-retinal (retinaldehyde) and acid-retinoic acid. All three basic forms are found in two variants: with the β -ionone nucleus (vitamin A1) and with the dehydrogenated β -ionone nucleus (vitamin A2). Vitamin A1 is both quantitatively and qualitatively more important as a source of vitamin A. Some compounds of the class of polyisoprenoid plant pigments called carotenoids yield retinoids on metabolism, and thus also have vitamin A activity. These are called provitamin A carotenoids and include β -carotene. Vitamin A in the visual process, as 11-*cis*-retinal, serves as the photosensitive chromophoric group of the visual pigments of rod and cone cells of the retina. Clinical signs of vitamin A deficiency include impaired dark adaptation, nyctalopia and ocular lesions. Vitamin A is essential for growth, fetal development and tissue maintenance. Vitamin A deficiency is associated with malnutrition, especially protein-energy malnutrition. This deficiency can reduce hepatic cytochrome *P*-450 contents and related enzyme activities.

Plasma retinol levels are inversely related to the risk of ischemic stroke. It has been shown that low plasma β -carotene concentrations are associated with an increased risk of myocardial infarction. Chronic deprivation of vitamin A leads to anemia. Supplemental vitamin A has been shown to increase iron status in anemic, vitamin A-deficient patients. Retinoids are involved in the differentiation of myeloid cells into neutrophils in the bone marrow and therefore, vitamin A-deficient patients are typically more susceptible to infection. Alterations caused by vitamin A deficiency provide environments conducive to bacterial growth and secondary infection in loci obstructed by keratinizing debris. Active infection appears to alter the utilization or, at least, the distribution of vitamin A among tissues. For example, it has been shown that plasma retinol concentrations drop during malarial attacks, chickenpox, diarrhea, measles and respiratory diseases³.

In populations where vitamin A availability from food is low, infectious diseases can precipitate vitamin A deficiency by decreasing intake and absorption, and increasing excretion (there may be up to 8-fold increase in the urinary excretion of retinol and retinol binding protein during

episodes of an acute infection). Vitamin A deficiency impairs innate immunity by impeding normal regeneration of mucosal barriers damaged by infection, and by diminishing the function of neutrophils, macrophages, and natural killer (NK) cells. Vitamin A is also required for adaptive immunity and plays an important role in the development of both T- and B-cells. Vitamin A deficiency diminishes antibody-mediated responses directed by T-helper-2 (Th2) cells, but some aspects of Th1-mediated immunity are also diminished. Changes in mucosal epithelial regeneration and immune function presumably account for the increased mortality seen in vitamin A-deficient infants, young children, and pregnant women⁴. Vitamin deficiencies and infections caused by viruses and other pathogens often coexist and exhibit complex interactions. The leading causes of death, particularly in children, especially in the developing countries are malnutrition, including vitamin A deficiency and consequent increased susceptibility for infections⁵.

A molecular docking study showed that a novel receptor STRA6 (signaling receptor and transporter of retinol 6) may play a critical role in the pathogenicity of COVID-19: spike protein receptor binding domain of

SARS-CoV-2 strongly and efficiently binds to STRA6 receptor, which is a membrane receptor responsible for signaling and transporting of vitamin A (retinol) from plasma retinol binding protein to cells⁶. In another study, bioinformatics analysis and computation assays using a network pharmacology method were conducted to explore and uncover the therapeutic targets and mechanisms of vitamin A for treating COVID-19. These findings indicate that the mechanisms of vitamin A action against SARS-CoV-2 include enrichment of immunoreaction, inhibition of inflammatory reaction, and biological processes related to reactive oxygen species. In addition to that, seven core targets of vitamin A against COVID-19, including mitogen-activated protein kinase 1 (MAPK1) and 14 (MAPK14), interleukin-10 (IL10), epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), intracellular adhesion molecule 1 (ICAM1), catalase (CAT), and protein kinase C beta type (*PRKCB*) were identified⁷.

The 12-week Apollo trial will investigate whether nasal drops containing the vitamin A may help patients who experienced smell loss or an altered sense of smell as a result of viral infections, including COVID-19⁸.

Available evidence shows that vitamin A deficiency is associated with an increased susceptibility for infections, including COVID-19, and that acute infection is decreasing intake and absorption, whilst increasing urinary excretion (up to 8-fold) of vitamin A, meaning that infection may worsen vitamin A deficiency, and therefore, close the vicious circle. In order to prevent and treat the vicious circle of vitamin A deficiency and increased susceptibility for infections and/or increased risk for severe infection, including COVID-19, prevention and treatment of vitamin A deficiency is important. There may be an increased need for vitamin A during the acute phase of infection, but more research is mandatory in order to determine the exact doses that might be helpful during the infection (these doses might be higher than the dose used to solely prevent the vitamin A deficiency and preserve optimal vitamin A levels whether is healthy balanced diet and/or vitamin A supplementation when necessary). There is some evidence showing that SARS-CoV-2 might be a STRA6 competitive inhibitor, leading to downregulation of STRA6 receptor, which causes the inhibition of the regulatory function of retinoic acid and cholesterol, all of which together may be

relevant for the development of COVID-19-associated lymphopenia, interferon inhibition, cytokine storm and smell loss. Therefore, systemic vitamin A supplementation and/or nasal drops containing vitamin A might be helpful in the alleviation of anosmia/hyposmia, as well as (valid only for systemic vitamin A supplementation) prevention and/or mitigation of cytokine storm, but clinical trials are mandatory in order to further elucidate this hypothesis.

VITAMIN B3 (NIACIN)

Niacin is the term describing pyridine 3-carboxylic acid and derivatives exhibiting qualitatively the biological activity of nicotinamide. Niacin functions metabolically as the essential component of the enzyme co-substrates nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide + hydrogen (NAD(H)) and nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate + hydrogen (NADP(H)). General signs of niacin deficiency (pellagra) are dermatitis, diarrhea, delirium and death³.

Researchers found in a study that genetic or pharmacological inhibition of *Candida albicans* enzyme Hst3 (histone 3) with nicotinamide strongly reduced *C. albicans* virulence in a mouse model. Both normal

and drug-resistant strains of *C. albicans* were susceptible to nicotinamide. In addition, nicotinamide prevented the growth of other pathogenic *Candida* species and *Aspergillus fumigatus*, thus demonstrating the broad antifungal properties⁹. It has been shown that increasing nicotinamide concentrations through pharmacological supplementation is consistent with the natural host response to both *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and HIV¹⁰.

The results of molecular docking analysis indicated that niacin exerted effective binding capacity in COVID-19. The pharmacology-based and computational analysis indicated that niacin could help in treating colorectal cancer/COVID-19 through cytoprotection, enhancement of immunologic functions, inhibition of inflammatory reactions and regulation of cellular microenvironment. Five core pharmacological targets of niacin in colorectal cancer/COVID-19 were identified, including Bcl-2-like protein 1 (BCL2L1), prostaglandin-endoperoxide synthase 2 (PTGS2), interleukin-1 beta (IL1B), interferon gamma (IFNG) and serine protease inhibitor clade E member 1 (SERPINE1)¹¹.

To conclude, there is some preclinical evidence showing that niacin might be relevant in some fungal (*Candida*, *Aspergillus*), viral (COVID-19, HIV) and bacterial (*Mycobacterium tuberculosis*) diseases, but more clinical research is needed.

PANTOTHENIC ACID (VITAMIN B5)

Pantothenic acid is a term describing the compound dihydroxy- β , β -dimethylbutyryl- β -alanine that has two metabolically active forms: coenzyme A, in which the vitamin is linked via a phosphodiester group with adenosine-3',5'-diphosphate, and acyl-carrier protein, in which it is linked via a phosphodiester to a serinyl residue of the protein. Panthenol is a provitamin, coenzyme A serves as an essential cofactor for about 4% of known enzymes and the acyl-carrier protein is a component of the multienzyme complex fatty acid synthase. Deprivation of pantothenic acid results in various metabolic impairments, including reduced lipid synthesis and energy production. Pantothenic acid deficiency may be associated with a decreased antibody production³.

PYRIDOXINE (VITAMIN B6)

Vitamin B6 is a term describing all 3-hydroxy-2-methylpyridine derivatives. The metabolically active form of vitamin B6 is pyridoxal phosphate, which serves as a coenzyme of numerous enzymes, most of which are involved in the metabolism of amino acids. Pyridoxal phosphate is involved in practically all amino acid metabolism reactions, in both their biosynthesis and their catabolism. Human studies have demonstrated effects of vitamin B6 deprivation on humoral-mediated immune responses with diminished antibody production and cell-mediated immune responses with reduced delayed-type hypersensitivity responses, reduced T-cell mediated cytotoxicity and reduced cytokine production³.

CYANOCOBALAMIN (VITAMIN B12)

Vitamin B12 is the generic descriptor for all corrinoids (compounds containing the corrin nucleus) exhibiting the qualitative biological activity of cyanocobalamin, which is the trivial designation of the vitamin B12-active corrinoid (also called cobalamin) with a cyano ligand (CN⁻) at the β position of the cobalt atom. *Helicobacter pylori* infection may cause the type B chronic atrophic

gastritis, which is associated with hypochlorhydria that facilitates the proliferation of bacteria in the intestine. The consequence is low enteric absorption of vitamin B12. Tropical sprue and ileitis involve damage to the ileal epithelium that can cause the loss of ileal intrinsic factor receptors. Intestinal parasites such as the fish tapeworm *Diphyllobothrium latum* can effectively compete with the host for uptake of this vitamin. Explosively growing bacterial floras can do likewise. Protozoal infections such as *Giardia lamblia*, which cause chronic diarrhea, appear to cause vitamin B12 malabsorption in malnourished individuals³.

Results of a cohort study showed that combined oral supplementation containing vitamin D (1000 IU daily), magnesium (150 mg daily) and vitamin B12 (500 mcg daily) in older COVID-19 patients (≥ 50 years) was associated with a significant reduction in the proportion of patients with clinical deterioration requiring oxygen support (17.6 vs 61.5%, $P=0.006$; odds ratio 0.13), intensive care support (odds ratio 0.20), or both¹².

Gastrointestinal infections (bacterial overgrowth, *Giardia lamblia*,

Diphyllobothrium latum, tropical sprue, *Helicobacter pylori*) cause malabsorption of vitamin B12, and thus represent a risk factor for the development of vitamin B12 deficiency. One study showed promising results for combined oral supplementation consisting of vitamin D, magnesium and vitamin B12 in the prevention of severe form of COVID-19 in elderly patients.

VITAMIN C

Vitamin C is a term describing all compounds exhibiting qualitatively the biological activity of ascorbic acid, which is involved in synthesis of collagen, degradation of 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate, synthesis of norepinephrine and desaturation of fatty acids. Ascorbic acid can also act as an antioxidant. It can stimulate the production of interferons, positive chemotactic and proliferative responses of neutrophils, the synthesis of humoral thymus factor and antibodies of the IgG and IgM classes³. Vitamin C contributes to healthy immune defense system by supporting various cellular functions of both the innate and adaptive immune system. It supports epithelial barrier function against pathogens and promotes the oxidant scavenging activity of the skin. It accumulates in

phagocytic cells, such as neutrophils, and can enhance chemotaxis, phagocytosis, generation of reactive oxygen species, and microbial killing. It is also important for apoptosis and clearance of the spent neutrophils from sites of infection by macrophages. Vitamin C may enhance differentiation and proliferation of both B- and T-cells. Vitamin C deficiency results in impaired immunity and higher susceptibility to infections, and *vice versa*, infections may lower body levels of vitamin C due to enhanced inflammation and metabolic requirements (vicious circle). Therefore, supplementation with vitamin C may be relevant for the prevention and treatment of respiratory and systemic infections¹³.

A systematic literature review showed that up to year 2017 a total of 148 animal studies indicated that vitamin C may alleviate or prevent infections caused by bacteria, viruses, and protozoa. Two controlled clinical trials found a statistically significant dose-response on the duration of common cold symptoms with up to 6-8 g/day of vitamin C, three controlled trials found that vitamin C prevented pneumonia, two controlled trials found a treatment benefit of vitamin C for pneumonia patients and one

controlled trial reported treatment benefits for tetanus patients¹⁴.

There is some evidence showing that vitamin C and quercetin co-administration exerts a synergistic antiviral action due to overlapping antiviral and immunomodulatory properties, and the capacity of ascorbate to recycle quercetin, which increases its efficacy, and therefore, this combination might be helpful as prophylaxis and adjunct treatment of COVID-19¹⁵.

Vitamin C is important for the maintenance of both T- and B-cell immunity. Vitamin C deficiency and infections may close the vicious circle in which low vitamin C levels predispose individuals to infections and infections further lower body levels of vitamin C. Although there is not enough data from clinical trials to support the use of vitamin C in the context of COVID-19 pandemic, available knowledge about vitamin C implicates that optimal levels of this vitamin are important factor in immune system conditioning and therefore, patients suffering from vitamin C deficiency may be predisposed to more severe form of COVID-19. Combination of vitamin C and quercetin as prophylaxis and an adjunct therapy for

COVID-19 may be an interesting hypothesis for further research.

VITAMIN D

Vitamin D is the generic descriptor for all steroids exhibiting qualitatively the biological activity of cholecalciferol (vitamin D3), which is produced metabolically through a natural process of photolysis of 7-dehydrocholesterol on the surface of skin exposed to ultraviolet irradiation (sunlight). The metabolically active forms of vitamin D are ring- (at C-1) and side chain-hydroxylated derivatives of vitamins D2 (ergocalciferol) and D3. Vitamin D has an important influence on the body's immune system by modulating the innate and adaptive immune system, influencing the production of important endogenous antimicrobial peptides such as cathelicidin, and regulating the inflammatory cascade³. The molecular data infer that vitamin D signaling should boost innate immunity against bacterial and viral pathogens. It also suppresses inflammatory immune responses that underlie autoimmunity and regulate allergic responses¹⁶. In immune cells, expression of CYP27B1, the 25-hydroxyvitamin D 1 α -hydroxylase, is induced by immune-specific

inputs, leading to local production of hormonal 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D (1,25D) at sites of infection, which in turn directly induces the expression of genes encoding antimicrobial peptides. 1,25-vitamin D stimulates autophagy which has been shown to be critical for the control of intracellular pathogens such as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. 1,25-vitamin D is also active in signaling cascades that promote innate immunity and therefore, poor vitamin D status is associated with greater susceptibility to viral infections¹⁷.

Vitamin D may exert several mechanisms of reducing the risk of acute respiratory tract infections, including COVID-19: reduction of survival and replication of viruses, reduction of the risk of inflammatory cytokine production, increase of angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 concentrations and the maintenance of endothelial integrity. Data from observational studies show that serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D concentrations are inversely correlated with the incidence or severity of COVID-19¹⁸. The most protective effect of vitamin D supplementation can be seen in patients deficient in vitamin D (serum 25(OH)D levels < 10 ng/mL). Supplementation with daily or weekly doses of vitamin D, aimed at increasing the

concentration of serum 25(OH)D to the optimal level of 30-50 ng/mL could be considered as an important factor of preventing the severe forms of COVID-19¹⁹.

Vitamin D is an immunomodulatory vitamin. Therefore, it is important in the maintenance of the optimal immune system response to bacterial and viral infections, including intracellular pathogens. It seems that optimal vitamin D levels are not only important for the promotion of adequate immune response to various pathogens, but are also important for the prevention of hyperinflammatory response, cytokine storm and autoimmunity, all of which together is especially important in the context of COVID-19 pandemic. It has been shown that both too weak immune response and hyperinflammatory immune response (cytokine storm) are associated with severe forms of COVID-19, and therefore, optimal vitamin D levels should be considered as an important protective factor.

VITAMIN E

Vitamin E is a term describing all tocol and tocotrienol derivatives that exhibit qualitatively the biological activity of α -tocopherol. These compounds are isoprenoid side-chain derivatives of 6-chromanol.

Vitamin E, a potent lipid-soluble antioxidant, found in higher concentration in immune cells compared to other cells in blood, is one of the most effective nutrients known to modulate immune function. Vitamin E deficiency has been demonstrated to impair the normal functioning of the immune system³. Vitamin E modulates T cell function through directly impacting T cell membrane integrity, signal transduction, and cell division, and also indirectly by affecting inflammatory mediators generated from other immune cells²⁰. Results of a study aimed to investigate the effects of vitamin E (VE) on the immune system and tumor growth during radiotherapy (RT) in mice model, showed that the number of leukocytes was increased in the VE group, the magnitude of leukocyte recovery after RT was also increased by VE with the note that this change was affected largely by alterations in lymphocytes and monocytes. Both CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T lymphocytes were positively affected by VE. In addition to that, tumor growth was inhibited not only by RT but also by VE alone with the evidence of synergistic effect when RT was combined with VE²¹.

Vitamin E is another immunomodulatory vitamin, important for the normal function of

the immune system, protecting the host from both infection and hyperinflammatory syndrome. Therefore, an optimal vitamin E status might be considered as an important factor in the prevention and treatment of severe forms of infections, including severe form of COVID-19.

VITAMIN K

Vitamin K is the generic descriptor for 2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone and all of its derivatives exhibiting qualitatively the biological (antihemorrhagic) activity of phyloquinone. The eight vitamin K-dependent proteins in plasma are factors IIa, VII, IX and X, proteins C, S and Z. Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, such as biliary stasis, liver disease, cystic fibrosis, celiac disease and *Ascaris* infection can interfere with the enteric absorption of vitamin K. Sulfonamides and broad spectrum antibiotic drugs can virtually sterilize the lumen of the intestine, thus removing an important source of vitamin K³.

Results of a study suggested that vitamin K deficiency, which is greater in males, is frequently observed in COVID-19 patients. In male patients, vitamin K deficiency is associated with a greater IL-6 level in the general circulation. Researchers proposed

that vitamin K deficiency could support the development of cytokine storm by increasing inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, which is involved in the building up of the inflammatory response recruiting both cellular and humoral components. Vitamin K deficiency can also contribute to events involved in vascular calcification leading to thrombosis and disseminate intravascular coagulation (DIC), which feature the microvascular damage observed in COVID patients. Finally, authors concluded that vitamin K deficiency is a possible modifiable risk factor for a more severe evolution of COVID-19²². Results of another study showed that in early phase of acute COVID-19, both vitamin K and vitamin D deficiency were independently associated with worse COVID-19 disease severity. Participants who were vitamin D deficient (<20 ng/mL) had the worse vitamin K status (dp-ucMGP >780 ng/mL) and experienced the most severe COVID-19 outcomes, which suggests a potential synergistic interplay between these 2 vitamins in COVID-19²³.

DISCUSSION

Available evidence shows that vitamin A deficiency and infection close the vicious circle: vitamin A deficiency increases susceptibility for severe infection and *vice versa*, infections might worsen the severity of vitamin A deficiency because of an increased losses of vitamin A during the infection. Therefore, prevention and treatment of vitamin A deficiency might be relevant for the prevention of severe infections, including COVID-19, but clinical trials are mandatory in order to determine the exact dose of vitamin A that might be used during the infection, especially the severe ones, aside from standard nutritional interventions used to prevent vitamin A deficiency in general and specific populations (healthy balanced diet, fortification of food with vitamin A if necessary, standard vitamin A supplementation for vulnerable populations such as patients suffering from malnutrition and elderly). There is some evidence showing that SARS-CoV-2 might be a STRA6 competitive inhibitor, causing the downregulation of STRA6 receptor with consequent inhibition of the regulatory function of retinoic acid and cholesterol, which may be relevant in the development of

anosmia/hyposmia, weakened immune response (interferon system inhibition, lymphopenia) and cytokine storm, but clinical research is mandatory in order to determine whether systemic vitamin A supplementation and/or nasal drops containing vitamin A (valid only for the prevention and treatment of smell loss) have such clinical effects.

There is some preclinical evidence showing that niacin might be relevant in some fungal (*Candida*, *Aspergillus*), viral (COVID-19, HIV) and bacterial (*Mycobacterium tuberculosis*) diseases. The same, it has been mentioned in the available scientific literature that pantothenic acid deficiency might be associated with decreased antibody production. It has been also reported that pyridoxine is important for the normal functioning of both humoral and cell-mediated immunity. Gastrointestinal infections (bacterial overgrowth, *Giardia lamblia*, *Diphyllobothrium latum*, tropical sprue, *Helicobacter pylori*) can cause malabsorption of vitamin B12, and thus represent a risk factor for the development of vitamin B12 deficiency. One study showed promising results for the use of combined oral supplementation consisting of vitamin D, magnesium and vitamin B12 in the

prevention of severe form of COVID-19 in elderly patients.

Vitamin C is important for the maintenance of the healthy immune defense system. Vitamin C deficiency and infections close the vicious circle in which low vitamin C levels predispose individuals to infections and infections further lower body levels of vitamin C. Although there is not enough data from clinical trials to support the use of vitamin C in the context of COVID-19 pandemic, previous scientific knowledge implicates that optimal levels of vitamin C represent an important factor in immune system conditioning and therefore, patients suffering from vitamin C deficiency may be predisposed to more severe forms of COVID-19.

Vitamin D as an immunomodulatory vitamin is important in the maintenance of the optimal immune system response to bacterial and viral infections, including intracellular pathogens. It seems that optimal vitamin D levels are not only important in the promotion of adequate immune response to various pathogens, but are also important for the prevention of hyperinflammatory response, cytokine storm and autoimmunity, all of which together is especially important

in the context of COVID-19 pandemic. It has been shown that both too weak immune response and hyperinflammatory immune response (cytokine storm) are associated with severe forms of COVID-19, and therefore, optimal vitamin D levels should be considered as an important protective factor. Vitamin E is another immunomodulatory vitamin, important for the normal functioning of the immune system, protecting the host from both infection and hyperinflammatory syndrome. Therefore, an optimal vitamin E status might be an important factor in the prevention and treatment of severe forms of infections, including COVID-19.

Vitamin K deficiency has been recognized to be an important modifiable risk factor for more severe form of COVID-19 because it is associated with higher levels of proinflammatory cytokine IL-6 in general circulation, it may support the development of cytokine storm, and it can also contribute to events involved in vascular calcification with consequent thrombosis and DIC. It has also been observed that patients who are vitamin D deficient may have worse vitamin K status leading to the more severe form of COVID-19.

CONCLUSION

Based on the previous scientific knowledge it is clear that optimal nutritional status, especially of vitamins A, C, E and D, is important for the normal functioning of the immune system. It seems that infections can increase the expenditure of vitamins A and C, and *vice versa*, lower levels of vitamin A and C may be associated with an increased susceptibility for infections and increased risk for the development of severe forms of infection, including COVID-19. Immunomodulatory vitamins D and E are important for the optimization of immune response to various infections, protecting thus the host from both severe forms of infection and hyperinflammatory immune response with the development of cytokine storm and/or autoimmune processes, which is especially important in the context of COVID-19 pandemic. It seems that vitamin K deficiency is an important modifiable risk factor for the development of severe forms of COVID-19 and that vitamin D and vitamin K deficiency are interrelated, and represent potentially a synergistic effect on the severity of COVID-19, but further research on this subject is necessary. There may be an interesting synergistic prophylactic and therapeutic effect of

vitamin C and quercetin supplementation against severe forms of COVID-19, what may be an interesting subject for further research. Some evidence shows that vitamins B3, B5, B6 and B12 also play an important role in the normal functioning of the immune defense system.

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